

Best practice protocol for the Validation of Engineering Models (MOTIVATE Protocol)

Erwin Hack
Eann Patterson
Ksenija Dvurecenska
George Lampeas
Thorsten Siebert

19 Jun 2020

Erwin Hack
Empa
Swiss Federal Laboratories for
Materials Science and Technology
Dübendorf, Switzerland

Eann A Patterson
A A Griffith Chair in Structural Materials &
Mechanics
Dean of the School of Engineering
University of Liverpool
Liverpool, United Kingdom

George Lampeas
I.S.I. - Industrial Systems Institute
Patras Science Park
Patras, Greece

Ksenija Dvurecenska
School of Engineering
Mechanical, Materials and Aerospace
Engineering
University of Liverpool
Liverpool, United Kingdom

Thorsten Siebert
LaVision GmbH
Goettingen, Germany

The MOTIVATE project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 754660. This document reflects only the authors' view and the JU is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	4
2. Overview on the MOTIVATE Protocol.....	4
2.1 Inputs	6
2.2 Historical Simulation Data Evaluation.....	7
2.3 Historical Measurement Data Evaluation	10
2.4 Modelling & Simulation	13
2.5 Physical Testing.....	15
2.6 Quantitative Comparison.....	17
2.7 Decision Maker's Review	18
3. Discussion and conclusions.....	19
References	20

Executive Summary

This 'MOTIVATE Protocol' describes best practice for the validation process for a structural model and can serve as a validation guideline. It incorporates the outcomes from the H2020 Clean Sky 2 project, MOTIVATE. It is based on the MOTIVATE validation flowchart and has been detailed into a step-by-step procedure which was refined during a test on an Airbus artefact in the project.

1. Introduction

This document arose from the *H2020 Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking* project MOTIVATE¹. It describes a best practice protocol (or "MOTIVATE Protocol" for short) for a validation process for a structural model. The MOTIVATE Protocol follows the novel flowchart² developed in the MOTIVATE project. It is intended to be more relevant to industrial applications than the generic one found in the well-known ASME V&V guide³. It provides specific step-by-step guidance to lead a responsible engineer through the process of model validation, including appraisal of historical data as well as defining, requesting, performing and evaluating a validation experiment. Test definitions and test request protocols should ensure compatibility and comparability of the predicted data from a simulation and measurement data from a validation experiment so that the physical test campaign, if needed at all, can be optimized. The MOTIVATE Protocol further includes the comparison of data sets as well as an evaluation of the quality of the data for the intended use, based on a quantitative validation metric⁴.

2. Overview on the MOTIVATE Protocol

The MOTIVATE Validation Flowchart, reproduced in Fig. 1, forms the basis of the MOTIVATE Protocol. A key novel feature is the evaluation of historical data. In addition, the development of the model takes priority, while physical testing is performed only if required. The processes involved are shown as coloured boxes. This includes the decision sequence required to evaluate historical data for use in the validation process and the quantitative validation process described in the recently published CEN guide⁵ which is currently being transformed into a CEN Technical Report, and supplemented by a validation metric⁴. As in the CEN guide, it is assumed here that data fields can be measured and are used in the comparison with corresponding fields predicted by a computational model; and, in addition, image decomposition is deployed to enable such comparisons. To allow for an unbiased comparison of the data sets, it is recommended to implement a "double blind" procedure. To this end, interaction of the testing and modelling teams are only allowed as far as to clarify and agree on test object, geometry, boundary conditions and load cases. Then, data are generated by experiment (see blue box in Fig. 1) and by simulation (see orange box in Fig. 1) independently, and the results are transferred to an independent validation team who is in charge of the Quantitative Comparison (see red box in Fig. 1). It should be noted that, prior to starting the validation process, it will be necessary for decision-makers to state their expectations so that appropriate decision criteria can be adopted, for instance requirements for measurement uncertainty. While this activity of the decision-makers was not within the brief of the MOTIVATE project, their review at the end of the process is shown for completeness and comparison with the existing ASME flowchart³.

In what follows we describe the step-by-step procedure, maintaining the colour coding of the flowchart for visualizing the main building blocks, and present a tabulated description of the inputs, processes and outputs which could be used to develop documentation in the form of evidence profiles that are essential to establish credibility in predictions. Guyatt et al.⁶ have recommended that evidence profiles should be succinct, transparent and easily digestible summaries of evidence; while Sargent⁷ has stated that both a summary and a detailed documentation is required.

Fig. 1: The MOTIVATE validation flowchart, updated relative to Hack et al.² following user feedback. The coloured boxes represent sub-charts broken out in tabular form over the next sections.

2.1 Inputs

The definition of the validation case includes the identification of the object of interest, the intended purpose of the model, the parameter(s) on which validation shall be based – preferably, displacement or strain field components – and the requested level of accuracy.

Item	Steps / Examples
Object of interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • State the structure and physical context of the model/simulation. • State the application context, e.g. fatigue, ultimate load, or occurrence of buckling.
Intended purpose of the model/simulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List the use to which the predictions from the model/simulation will be put, for instance the decisions to be informed by the predictions and their consequences e.g. predicting failure modes or safe operating conditions.
Properties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List the essential properties of the object of interest, e.g. material properties. • List load envelope, expected mechanics and associated properties, e.g. contact physics; fracture mechanics; ultimate load; or elastic loading regime.
Geometry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List the detailed geometry, e.g. fastener type and spacing, or component thickness.
Existing knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List expected behaviour regimes and, or physics domains and the appropriate laws of physics, engineering principles and materials science. • List current accepted paradigm including the underlying assumptions. • List current state of modelling. • List origin of the object of interest, e.g. type designation.
Decision criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • State the criteria to be used for assessing the outcome of the validation procedure, preferably in collaboration with the decision maker.

2.2 Historical Simulation Data Evaluation

In some cases, the validation of simulation results can be performed through comparison with results from a model previously validated for the same conditions⁸. These data might be available in a validation database set up according to a Data Management Plan (historical data). However, only models of evolutionary designs with incremental changes in comparison to the previous model can be evaluated, whereas this is not applicable for models with, e.g. a radical design change or new physics, new mechanics or new materials⁹ (unexplored region).

Item	Steps / Comments
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is the design significantly different with major changes / improvements? • Is the behaviour of the design likely to be in a different physics domain, e.g. has non-linearity been introduced, or fluid-solid-interaction? • Is a different class of material being modelled? e.g. transition from homogeneous to heterogeneous, from isotropic to anisotropic material parameters; from Aluminium to CFRP. • Are different mechanics likely to govern the response, e.g. in joints or evolving contact?
	<p>If the answer is «Yes», i.e. one or several of the above questions are answered affirmatively:</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specify the new physical laws / new mechanical behaviour / new material properties. • State the new modelling regime and validation envelope.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specifications for the new simulations, including design, geometry, physical laws, materials, load ranges.

<p>Radical Design Change or New Physics/Mechanics/Materials ?</p>	<p>If the answer is «No»:</p>
<p>Prior models Assumptions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> List available CAD models and/or computational models of the related objects. List historical data sets simulated with these models. List the assumptions made in the prior models.
<p>Assessment of Historical Data</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the data documentation complete, including uncertainty/sensitivity analysis? Are load cases and boundary conditions known? Is the modelling detail sufficient?
<p>Relevance of Historical Data</p>	<p>Statement of the relevance of the historical simulation results relative to decision criteria for the validation process.</p>
<p>Prior model sufficient?</p>	<p>If the answer is «No»:</p>
<p>Specify new / additional simulations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> State the (novel) material system to be validated. e.g. use of CFRP panels instead of aluminium sheets State the (novel) structure to be validated, e.g. gluing instead of fasteners. State novel mechanics and, or physics.
<p>Specification for new/additional simulations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specifications for additional/new simulations, including design, geometry, physical laws, materials, load ranges.
<p>Prior model sufficient?</p>	<p>If the answer is «Yes», answer the following questions:</p>

<p>Validation available & adequate?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Has the prior model been validated? • Are the actual validation requirements/parameters (decision criteria) met by the prior model validation? • Is the validation envelope filled? e.g. load and dynamic ranges <p>If the answer is «Yes», provide:</p>
<p>Prior Predictions, Uncertainty, Modelling Credentials & Validation Metric</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality assurance documents and modelling credentials. • Statement of boundary conditions and load cases. • Simulation results and their uncertainties from the relevant data base, assembled in a form useable for the validation process. • Report on the predictions, uncertainties and modelling credentials.
<p>Validation available & adequate?</p>	<p>If the answer is «No», i.e. validation of the prior model was insufficient:</p>
<p>Specify Validation Experiment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specify (additional) validation experiment(s). • State the measurement parameters on which to base the validation process e.g. out-of-plane displacement field, in-plane strain field. • State the acceptance level and the validation metric to be used. • State the data formats to be used in the comparison and the link to the Data Management Plan. • Issue a test request.
<p>Specification for Validation Experiment</p> <p>Prior Predictions, Uncertainty & Modelling Credentials</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Artefact to be used. • Load cases. • Measurement parameters and target uncertainty. • Data format. • Simulation results and their uncertainties from the relevant data base, assembled in a form useable for the validation process.

2.3 Historical Measurement Data Evaluation

For some model validation tasks, data from experiments¹⁰ performed previously, and included in databases, might be available (historical data). When information on the accuracy of these experimental results is insufficient, an adequate confidence level might not be obtained¹¹. This promotes the need for new experiments in order to obtain the necessary information¹².

Item	Steps / Comments
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the design significantly different with major changes/improvements? Is the behaviour of the object likely to be in a different physics domain? e.g. has non-linearity been introduced, or fluid-solid-interaction? Is a different class of material being used, e.g. transition from homogeneous to heterogeneous; from isotropic to anisotropic material parameters; from Aluminium to CFRP? Are different mechanics likely to govern the response, e.g. transition from rivets to glue in joints or evolving contact? <p>If the answer is «Yes», i.e. one or several of the above questions are answered affirmatively:</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specify the (additional) validation experiment(s). State the measurement parameters on which to base the validation process e.g. out-of-plane displacement field, or in-plane strain field component. State the validation metric to be used and the acceptance level. State the data formats to be used in the comparison. Issue a test request.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Artefact to be used. Load cases. Measurement parameters and target uncertainty. Data format.

<p>Radical Design Change or New Physics/Mechanics/ Materials ?</p>	<p>If the answer is «No»:</p>
<p>Available physical artefacts Available measurements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> List available artefacts and their relationship to the object of interest and intended use of the model. State the overall geometry and verify the details, e.g. by acquiring data describing the initial imperfections using DIC measurements or an alternative full-field technique for 3D shape measurement. List the material parameters and detailed geometry of the structure. List origin of component (e.g. type designation). State process of component preparation (including method of sampling components if appropriate). Provide available test descriptions and quality documents. Provide the available test data and their uncertainties plus any data from non-destructive evaluations.
<p>Assessment of Historical Data</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the data documentation complete, including specification of material and geometry? Are load cases and boundary conditions known? Is the level of uncertainty acceptable?
<p>Relevance of Historical Data</p>	<p>Statement of the relevance of historical data relative to the decision criteria.</p>

<p>Historical Data sufficient?</p>	<p>If the answer is «No»:</p>
<p>Specify Validation Experiments</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specify the (additional) validation experiment(s) State the measurement parameters on which to base the validation process e.g. out-of-plane displacement field, or in-plane strain field component. State the acceptance level and the validation metric to be used. State the data format to be used in the comparison. Issue a test request.
<p>Specification for Validation Experiment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Artefact to be used. Load cases. Measurement parameters and target uncertainty. Data format.

<p>Historical Data sufficient?</p>	<p>If the answer is «Yes»:</p>
<p>Historical Measurement Data & Uncertainty</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> List the experimental data in a form useable for the validation process. List the specific relevant boundary conditions and load cases for the simulation team. Full-field measurement data (data arrays, matrices or images). Measurement uncertainty of the data. Test specifications and meta-data. Auxiliary measures, e.g. load-displacement curves, temperature.

2.4 Modelling & Simulation

The simulations will provide predictions of data fields for the validation parameter(s) together with their uncertainties. Below, we state the steps to be taken following the six phases included in the work of Oberkampff et al. ^{13,14}. The first two phases are summarized as “Speculation” in the sub-chart of the MOTIVATE flowchart, the next two as “Articulation”, following the terminology of Hacking¹⁵ and Kuhn¹⁶; after which the “Model” is available as an output.

Phase	Item	Steps/Comments
Speculation	Conceptual Modelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> List relevant physical phenomena and the coupling of different physical processes. Identify all potential factors that could affect the validation requirements, e.g. by listing the most sensitive simulation parameters.
	Mathematical Modelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> State the analytical/mathematical representation of the problem. Provide a link to the verification documentation. State the appropriate initial and boundary values for the model and all its sub-models.
Articulation	Model Discretization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> List the software package to be used to develop the model parametrically and to enable the studying of the influence of model features on component behaviour. State, in an analytical form, all the spatial and temporal differencing methods, discretization of the boundary conditions, discretization of the geometric boundaries and grid generation methods.
	Discrete Model Programming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> State code limitations and practices of software quality assurance. Provide evidence of verification and convergence studies.
	Model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Verified model and its supporting documentation.
	Modelling credentials	Modelling credentials include:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Components of model praxis, e.g. neglected parameters, ‘rules of thumb’, choice of differencing schemes, exploitation of symmetry; • Collated historical evidence for reliability of each component of modelling praxis and for their integrated use; • Characterization associated with theoretical concepts.
<p style="text-align: center;">Solving Model</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List values of input parameters, e.g. grid spacing, material parameters, damping coefficients, load cases. • For a preliminary load case – that is below the critical load or load level of interest – ensure results from the model are consistent with the measurement parameters and boundary conditions; if necessary, perform iterations of the solution. • List output values and uncertainties, e.g. by Monte Carlo solutions using a variation of parameters, properties and the level of detail. • Provide evidence of fulfilment of accuracy requirements. • List output values and uncertainties for all other load cases without any further reference to the experiment to not jeopardize the “double-blind test”. • State in a report the predictions and associated uncertainty together with relevant meta data as specified by the team performing Quantitative Comparison and in accordance with the Data Management System.
<p style="text-align: center;">Predictions & Uncertainty</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Processed data for comparison with experimental and/or other virtual data in appropriate format, i.e. predictions and their uncertainties. • Description of Regions of Interest (ROIs)

2.5 Physical Testing

In the VANESSA project¹⁷, a need to design experiments specifically for the purpose of validation was recognized, when insufficient historical measurement data were available. The test-set up must be devised so that the full-field parameters, required for validation, can be measured from an optically-accessible surface, the area of comparison being as large as possible, but with sufficient spatial resolution in the regions of interest, in order to maximise confidence and credibility in the simulation results.

Load cases are established in such a way that the validated ‘envelope’ for the simulation matches its intended purposes. The aim is to optimise the test matrix inside this envelope to minimize time and cost while maximizing the reliability and confidence in the simulation.

The uncertainty of a DIC measurement can be assessed according to the procedure established in Siebert et al.¹⁸, and combined with the measurement uncertainties induced by the experimental set-up.

As it is paramount to obtain comparability of model results and experimental data sets, it might be necessary to modify the numerical models and repeat simulations in order to account for the experimental boundary conditions, such as those imposed by the device for introducing the load. This will ensure that test and simulation are ‘intertwined’ allowing for a rigorous, robust and meaningful comparison. However, no test data intended to be used in the data comparison step should be made available to the modellers.

Item	Comments
<div style="border: 1px solid black; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: fit-content; margin: auto;">Design of Experiments</div>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> List the appropriate test environment and loading machine / test rig, taking account of the load and deformation envelope set for the validation process. State regions of interest (ROIs) on the test specimen, e.g. allowing multiple views to capture global and local features. List the camera-based equipment and additional measurement devices , e.g. strain gauges, transducers for measuring load and displacement. State the appropriate locations (on the specimen/ at the machine/ in the laboratory) for the installation of the instrumentation. Provide a test plan including time-line. State load cases and load levels to match the intended use. Provide an optimized test matrix to minimize the number of physical tests. State a corresponding decision hierarchy for the load sequence. State the overall data quality and combined standard uncertainty. Confirm fulfilment of decision criteria.
<div style="border: 1px solid black; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: fit-content; margin: auto; transform: rotate(-15deg);">Test set-up & protocols</div>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specification of test and measurement equipment. Test protocol including load cases and test sequence.
<div style="border: 1px solid black; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: fit-content; margin: auto;">Perform Experiments</div>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Confirm performance of the experiments according to the test specifications and protocol. Provide a test report to the team responsible for Quantitative Comparison, respecting “double-blind” conditions, and to the Data management system.
<div style="border: 1px solid black; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: fit-content; margin: auto; transform: rotate(-15deg);">Measurements & Uncertainty</div>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Post-processed data for comparison with simulation data in appropriate format Report of results, including data fields for validation and experimental measurement uncertainty and a description of Regions of Interest.

2.6 Quantitative Comparison

The CEN guide⁵ (CEN Workshop Agreement) on the validation of computational solid mechanics models forms the scientific foundation of the quantitative comparison of full-field data, e.g. obtained from calibrated DIC systems. Although in the present work the comparison involves field data, such as displacement fields on the entire surface of a component, it is essential to offer the option of incorporating single point data, such as buckling loads or additional single point deformation/strain measurements.

A validation metric should be applied in the statistical comparison to measure the extent to which the model represents the real-world measurement data. The outcome of the validation metric is a quantity that can be easily interpreted to determine whether the model predictions are adequate for the intended use. To ensure an unbiased data comparison, it is suggested that three independent teams perform the experiments, the simulations and the comparison, respectively.

Item	Comments
Data assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> State the data fields (image/matrix representation of validation parameters) obtained from both the simulation team and the experimentation team and confirm they are for the same load cases, the same regions of interest, the same coordinate system, and the same validation parameters.
Data Decomposition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> State the type and controlling parameters used to decompose data fields as described in the CEN guide⁵, e.g. 4th order Chebyshev polynomials.
Feature Vectors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feature vectors for each pair of data fields and the corresponding reconstruction errors and correlation coefficients.
Statistical Comparison	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> State the total measurement uncertainty as described in the CEN guide. Provide a graph of the measured and predicted elements of the feature vectors together with the expanded uncertainty bounds. State the value of the validation metric to give the quantitative level of agreement, e.g. using one based on relative error⁴.
Representation of real-world [described by a validation metric]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The graph comparing the elements of the feature vectors describing the predictions and measurements, including the measurement uncertainty band $\pm 2u$. Value of the validation metric.

The outcome from this evaluation will both inform decision-making based on the simulation results and enhance confidence and credibility in simulations. To aid interpretation during the decision-making process, the degree of confidence in the metric representing the discrepancy or similarity between the data should be presented. A sample statement from a previously published case study of a rubber block indented by a wedge¹⁹ was expressed as: *'there is an 83% probability that the model is representative of the real world, when simulating x-direction displacements induced by a 2mm indentation, based on experimental data with a 10% relative uncertainty.* The first part of this statement, which refers to the probability, presents the quantitative validation outcome, i.e. the degree to which the model is an accurate representation of reality of interest based on the ASME³ philosophy; the second part of the statement summarises the validation case, e.g. displacement induced by indentation; and the last part states the quality of the measured data, used in the validation process, as an indication of the level of confidence in the validation outcome. The implementation of this type of statement would represent a significant advance on current practice and could be interpreted relatively straightforwardly by decision-makers. The outcome of these metrics allows the decision-maker, e.g. customer or stakeholder, to make the final judgment based on the evidence from the validation and their required or desired level of quality.

2.7 Decision Maker's Review

The final step, 'Decision Maker's Review', was beyond the scope of the MOTIVATE project and thus is not described in detail here, see for example Kaiser et al²⁰. In brief, the comparison outcome would be assessed against the accuracy requirements for the intended use of the model. Model credentials will be taken into account in a weighted way.

3. Discussion and conclusions

Throughout this document, it is assumed that data fields can be measured in physical tests and predicted by computational models; and, following the CEN guide⁵, it is recommended that image decomposition, or orthogonal decomposition, should be used to represent these data fields in a reduced dimensional format²¹. In other words, the fields of displacement and, or strain should be treated as images and decomposed following the techniques pioneered by Mottershead and his co-workers²² during the ADVISE project²³. In the MOTIVATE project, we have explored the use of Principal Components Analysis (PCA) as an alternative to orthogonal decomposition and concluded that it is less useful in a validation process because it is more difficult to control the components and ensure that corresponding components from measured and predicted data fields are being compared. Hence, the use of PCA in this context is not recommended.

The evaluation of the CEN guide performed during the VANESSA project¹⁹ highlighted the need to ensure that the regions of interest in the measured and predicted data fields were coincident and, parallel work demonstrated the use of tiles to allow data fields with complicated shapes to be decomposed using a generic decomposition algorithm. In MOTIVATE a generic algorithm for image decomposition has been produced that can handle data fields with irregular shapes including cut-outs and holes in the data field²⁴.

We have made no attempt to link the flowchart to the PCMM4²⁵ and its method for grading levels 0 through 4 to maturity of the tool elements which comprise:

1. CVER Code Verification
2. PMMF Physics and Material Model Fidelity
3. RGF Representation and Geometric Fidelity
4. SVER Solution Verification
5. VAL Validation
6. UQ Uncertainty Quantification

References

- ¹ MOTIVATE, Matrix Optimization for Testing by Interaction of Virtual and Test Environments, H2020 Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking, Grant Agreement No 754660
- ² Hack E, Dvurecenska K, Lampeas G, Patterson EA, Siebert T, Szigeti E, *Steps towards industrial validation experiments*, ICEM 2018, 01-05 July 2018, Brussels, Belgium, Proceedings **2** (2018) 391
- ³ ASME V&V 10-2006, Guide for verification & validation in computational solid mechanics, American Society of Mech. Engineers, New York, 2006.
- ⁴ Dvurecenska K, Graham S, Patelli E, Patterson EA. *A probabilistic metric for the validation of computational models*. Royal Society open science, **5**:11 (2018) 180687.
- ⁵ CEN, 2014, *Validation of computational solid mechanics models*, Brussels: Comité Européen de Normalisation (CEN), CWA 16799:2014. <https://www.cen.eu/work/areas/Materials/Pages/WS-71.aspx>
- ⁶ Guyatt GH, Oxman AS, Vist GE, Kunz R, Falck-Ytter Y, Schünemann HJ, *GRADE: what is 'quality of evidence' and why is it important to clinicians*, *BMJ*, 336 (2008)995-998.
- ⁷ Sargent RG, 2011, *Verification and validation of simulation models*, Proc. 2011 Winter Simulation Conference, S Jain, RR Creasey, J Himmelspach, KP White & M Fu eds., Piscataway, NJ: IEEE, 183-198.
- ⁸ Sargent RG, *An introduction to verification and validation of simulation models*, Proc. 2013 Winter Simulation Conference, 321-327.
- ⁹ Patterson EA, Whelan MP, *On the validation of variable fidelity multi-physics simulations*, *J Sound Vibration*, 448 (2019) 247-258
- ¹⁰ Oberkampf WL & Trucano TG, *Verification and Validation in Computational Fluid Dynamics*, Progress in Aerospace Sciences, 38:3 (2002)209-272.
- ¹¹ ASME, *An Illustration of the Concepts of Verification and Validation in Computational Solid Mechanics*, New York: American Society of Mechanical Engineers, ASME V&V 10.1-2012.
- ¹² Hack E, Lampeas G & Patterson EA, *An evaluation of a protocol for the validation of computational solid mechanics models*, *J. Strain Analysis*, 51:1 (2016) 5-13.
- ¹³ Oberkampf WL, Diegert KV, Alvin KF, Rutherford BM, *Variability, uncertainty, and error in computational simulations*. Presented at AIAA/ASME Joint Thermophys Heat Transfer Conf, Albuquerque, NM, 1998.
- ¹⁴ Oberkampf WL, DeLand SM, Rutherford BM, Diegert KV, Alvin KF, *A new methodology for the estimation of total uncertainty in computational simulation*. Presented at AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Struct, Struct Dyn, Mater Conf Exhibit, St. Louis, MO, 1999.
- ¹⁵ Hacking I, *Representing and intervening: introductory topics in the philosophy of science*. New York: Free Press, 1983.
- ¹⁶ Kuhn TS, 1977, Objectivity, value judgement and theory choice, in TS Kuhn, *The essential tension: selected studies in scientific tradition and change*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- ¹⁷ VANESSA, Validation of Numerical Engineering Simulations: Standardisation Action, EU FP7 project under Grant Agreement NMP3-SA-2012-319116
- ¹⁸ Siebert T, Hack E, Lampeas G, Patterson EA, Splitthoff K, *Uncertainty quantification for DIC measurements in industrial environments*, *Experimental Techniques*, submitted.
- ¹⁹ Vanessa ILS study, <http://www.engineeringvalidation.org/validation-ils>
- ²⁰ Kaizer JS, Heller AK & Oberkampf WL, 2015, *Scientific computer simulation review*, *Reliab. Eng. Syst. Saf.* 138 (2015) 210-218.
- ²¹ Lampeas G, Pasialis VP, Lin X & Patterson EA, *On the validation of solid mechanics models using optical measurements and data decomposition*, *Simulation Modelling Practice & Theory*, 52 (2015) 92-107.
- ²² Wang W, Mottershead JE, Sebastian CM, Patterson EA, *Shape features and finite element model updating from full-field strain data*, *Int. J. Solids Struct.* 48:11-12 (2011) 1644-1657.
- ²³ ADVISE, Advanced Dynamic Validations using Integrated Simulation and Experimentation, FP7 Grant Agreement No. 218595
- ²⁴ Dean A & Christian WJR, *Generalised decomposition of strain fields in complex components*, 14th Int. Conf. on Advances in Experimental Mechanics, Belfast, 10-12 September 2019.
- ²⁵ Hills RG, Witkowski WR, Rider WJ, Trucano TG, Urbina A, Development of a Fourth Generation Predictive Capability Maturity Model, Report SAND2013-8051, Sandia National Laboratories (2013)